

Impact of Social Media in Online Advertisement Industry

Bernice Titilola Gbadeyan¹, Bamidele Samuel Arije²

^{1,2}Department: Communication and Media Management Girne American University, North Cyprus

ABSTRACT: In a fast-changing world, trade proprietors, as well as marketers for both small scale businesses and enormous organization are attempting to overhaul their trade strategies in other not to become out of date in this progressing trade world. Days are long past when trade owners strive without the use of social media platforms. In these days of Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, and Instagram, social marketing has advanced as an indispensably portion of promoting business methodology. Therefore, in this advanced world, Social media platforms has recently become a well-known medium of creating awareness and is highly in use by both small and large business organizations. It is almost inconceivable to think of showcasing business and services without considering the significance of social media. However, embracing a few frames of online advanced social media platforms has ended up been fundamental for all trade houses. In an industry where patterns are changing in succession, selection of social network in showcasing business with the help of social media influencers is exceptionally crucial for companies to outlive in this race. In this paper, we attempt to discover the significance and effect of social media platforms in online advertising industry, and additionally to know how and the reason why business visionaries, as well as marketers, utilize social media in upgrading the changings in their products and services and business environment.

KEYWORDS: Social media, Business, Advertisement, Marketing and Influencers.

INTRODUCTION

The social media

Social media is an extensive concept that involved different interacting platform that gives room for individual to interact and share common ideas. However, Kent 2010, (p.645) opined that “Social Media” could be a wide concept encompassing different “interactive media channels that permit two-way interaction and criticism. In any case in a more unequivocal term, social media are computer intervened advances that encourage the creation and sharing of information, thought, career intrigued and other shapes of expression by means of virtual communities and systems. Obar, Jonathan, Wildman & Steve (2015) also asserted that social media are web2.0 empowered intuitively applications. According to Daluba and Maxwell (2013), it may well be said too that social media may be a means of intuitive among individuals of distinctive ages in which they make, share and trade data and concepts in virtual communities and arrange.

There are illustrations of social media stages and intelligently applications that have ruled the web space; the prevalent ones are Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Pinterest. Snapchat, WeChat, WhatsApp, Google+ and YouTube. They have comparable highlights such as interactivity, virtuality, immediate conveyance, interactive media record trade, interconnectivity and prompt input. Agreeing to Neese (2016), social media, a profoundly intuitively stage, may be a shape of modern media that relies heavily on the interest of clients to supply value. It is in any case critical to note that the nearness of the social media started with the coming of versatile phones and information empowering contraptions in year 2004, 2005 and 2006 individually, which made social media and other interactive applications an empowering stage to run. Valkenburg and Piotrowski (2017) expressed that; the breakthrough of the smartphone to the wide world started with the BlackBerry Pearl in 2006, which was taken after by the iPhone 2G in 2007- which before long got to be the fastest-selling contraption in history. Today, smartphones show up in each viewpoint of everyday life. More than any other media gadget, smartphones are inseparably connected with the utilize of social media.

SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS

The advert of internet has given individual the opportunity to advertise their business on the various social media platforms in this study, concentration will be on social media like Facebook, and Instagram.

Impact of Social Media in Online Advertisement Industry

FACEBOOK

Facebook analysts for the Business Insider, Carlson (2010) clarifies Facebook as a social medium that gives individuals the opportunity to share photographs, data, recordings and more. Individuals choose who can see their posts, whether it is freely or secretly amongst friends. From the starting, Facebook was a moment hit, Mark Zuckerberg launched “thefacebook.com” in the year 2004, and presently the page is way better known as “facebook.com” is one of the biggest social media platforms. Statista (2017a), viewed that, active users of Facebook within the third quarter of year 2017 were over 2.7 billion

INSTAGRAM

At the official site of Instagram (2017), they recognized Instagram as a social medium that gives individuals the opportunity to share with friends and people of like minds devotees’ previews communications between clients less demanding and user-friendly.

MARKETING

Concurring to Blackshaw and Nazzaro (2004) transactions with customers have changed significantly with the advent of Social media that is also referred to as consumer generated media. Spurgeon (2008) said that unused media stages and marketing methods have constrained marketers to reexamine their part in advertising. Nowadays promoters are not continuously the top-down communicators in the act of messages their brands, items or services, they are now making do with the promotion. Agreeing to Spurgeon, media consumers play a key part in advertising and particularly on social media. Spurgeon, also states that the customers are a dynamic portion of the method. With ever-changing market environment and innovation has changed the way marketers carry on, where and how they advertise.

ADVERTISING

The objective with advertisement is to begin with seizing the audience attention and creates a certain need, want or feeling. But with increased information, products, and administrations all around the world, it makes an indeed higher level of competition for companies to reach and connect with their customers. With increasing competition organizations ought to discover a better approach to reach their customer base and conceivable customers. Producers can utilize diverse strategies, like direct advertisement, word of mouth advertisements (WOM), supported advertisements, and hidden advertisement

Direct Advertisement

Everyday organizations disperse messages to their advertising section through media like e-mail, websites, mobile phones and social media like Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat, and Twitter.

Customers are always getting reminded around modern products or administrations, extraordinary offers, and bargains through diverse kind of media.

Word of Mouth Advertising

Koinets, Valck, Wojnicki, and Wilner (2010) conversation approximately how marketers point to impact the consumer's buying conduct, and one way of that's through word of mouth (WOM). They talk around WOM and how it works, with social media, the WOM has gotten to be a powerful marketing device that's difficult to control. Marketers can attempt to impact the communications that go on between customers. Therefore, with less demanding access customers are depending increasingly on the word-of mouth when it comes to choice making with respect to items or services. Information gathering, that the customer might do for illustration, with respect to the product, price or utilization, is disentangled with company websites, blogs, article audits and other social media platforms.

SOCIAL MEDIA CONSUMER MODEL.

The market is defined as a collection of buyers and sellers, in other words, consumers and producers, this two groups than communicate over products or services. As seen in figure 1 below, a simple marketing system defined, by Kotler and Keller, consists of these producers and consumers, in-between there is a flow of products, services, information, and communications. This marketing system in relation to social media can be explained as, information is where the advertisers and influencers communicate with the consumer, and by this communication we mean that the consumer gives feedback and review of the product or service to the producers/ organization.

Fig,1

SOCIAL MEDIA ADVERT INFLUNCERS

Social media influencers are people who work as bloggers on Facebook site, Snapchat, Instagram or a Twitter account. A few influencers are in use of these social media communities in all of these mediums. These influencers are looked at by producers as an individual that can be used for adverts for a brand or a product.

According to an interview published in Viðskiptablaðið (Gunnarsson, 2017), there MaríaHólmgrímsdóttir talked about influencers and, her definition is that an influencer is a certain role model that an individual looks to for advice regarding products or services. María is one of the owners of the social media agency, Eylenda.

DEFINITION OF INFLUENCER

Sweet wood (2017) expressed that influencers on social media are constantly marketing themselves and creating awareness as well as advertise the brand they support. This sort of promoting is characterized as individual branding that is the act of individuals showcasing themselves and advertising. Individual branding is about establishing a certain picture as a brand. With a solid and capable brand, 'followers' as used on social media will find that influencers fascinating and need to know more about the person the brand they support. Hence, it is imperative to discover an influencer who matches the item or the service. Going by a study conducted by Silvera and Austad (2004) with respect to demeanor towards the person promoting the product, it is necessary to find the right influencer for the product or services. The study come about that the consumer's discernment is affected by the feeling that the customer has towards that influencers truly just like the product or benefit or not.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Bandura's (1963) social learning theory has been widely used in academic study, notably in the domains of communication and advertising (Bush et al. 2004). It serves as a theoretical foundation for generating concepts for socializing agents that can anticipate consumer behavior (Martin and Bush 2000) According to social learning theory; an individual receives motivation and, as a result, adopts a positive attitude from socialization agents through either direct or indirect social contact (Moschis and Churchill 1978). This approach has been used in previous marketing research to analyze customer consumption behavior through various socialization agents such as celebrities, families, and friends.

Consequently, according to social learning theory, an individual's desire to purchase products is heavily influenced by the respondents' attitude and the efficiency of social media influencers (i.e., trustworthiness, source attractiveness, brand match-up, and meaning transfer) in brand promotion.

Impact of Social Media in Online Advertisement Industry

METHODOLOGY

Data for this study would be gotten through the qualitative research method which includes coordinated discussion, and individual research. The sort of qualitative research method that would connect in this research incorporates interviews, observations, secondary sources and data from social media analyst.

The qualitative study is a method of inquiry utilized in numerous diverse scholastic disciplines. Qualitative analysts point to accumulate an in-depth understanding of human behavior and the reasons that govern such behavior. (Veal, 2006.) The qualitative method can moreover be interpretive to its subject point and it gives the need to what the information has contributed to the investigation or interview question.

DISCUSSION

This study examines social media usage and advertising in general and the effects of social media influencers and the effect social media has on advertisements, and the consumer. Main results from this study show that advertising on social media does affect the consumer's behavior and attitude towards a product or a service. The effects are shown in the purchasing behavior, attitude and beliefs towards advertisements of the products and services. Other results show that influencers on social media do affect the consumer's behavior towards a product or service, in relation to purchasing behavior and reliability of the product or service.

Furthermore, the study revealed that advertising in general affects people's behavior, to an extent is difficult to predict.

In addition, the study shows that the purchasing behavior is affected, whether it is in relation to purchasing products that the consumer believes are necessary or unnecessary after seeing advertising on social media.

RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

Are consumers truly always in need of the products and services been advertised or is the advertisements that is influencing their purchasing behavior?

This study explores how social media advertisements affects consumer behavior towards a product or service. The focus of this study is based on the concept of marketing, advertising on social media. The results of this study reflect the author's suspicion that influencers on social media affect the consumer's behavior when it comes to the decision-making process of a product or a service. The study support that the more influencers you follow the more likely you are to purchase a product or a service that is being advertised, whether it is a direct advertisement, sponsorship or co-operation with an organization. The power of social media influencer cannot be underestimated when it comes to the consumer behavior towards advertising and products and services.

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Impact of Social Media in Online Advertisement Industry

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